

Corporate governance and profitability: An application of the Agency Theory

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Abstract

Several empirical studies have been conducted on the effects of corporate governance mechanisms on profitability. Some found significant positive associations, while others found significant negative associations, and still others have failed to find any significance at all. The majority of the work has been done in developed economies, and very little is known about emerging economies. In this regard, this piece interrogates the impact of corporation governance on bank return on equity in Corporate Nigeria. The paper examines 130 panel datasets of listed deposit money banks from 2010 to 2019 and found empirical evidence supporting negative significant effect of board ownership and audit committee size and positive insignificant effect of board independence and gender on return on equity. The effect of corporate age (as control variable) on profitability, on the other hand, was found to be negatively significant as well.

Keywords: *audit committee size, board independence, compensation, diversity, financial performance, ownership*

JEL classification: G2, G32, G34, L25

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1. Introduction

There is no single general theory explaining the nexus between corporate governance mechanisms (CGMs) and profitability (PROF) in developing countries. Different theories explain the association and there are no consistency in empirical findings among studies. Empirical literature show different results; some find significant and positive link, others find significant negative effect. Yet, others failed to find any relationship at all. As a result, this article investigates the influence of corporation governance on profitability among banks in Nigeria. It is true that profitability is the reward for business success, however, it is not the primary essence of business. Profitability is seen in the context of this paper as return on assets/equity. Return on assets is the proportion of earnings accruable to total assets. It is calculated as earnings after taxes divided by total assets. Similarly, return on equity is defined as earnings after taxes divided by equity. Profitability and financial performance are used interchangeably in this article since their measures are the same.

Several factors determine or affect profitability; including corporate governance mechanisms such as ownership structure, board size, independence, gender, meetings, remuneration, and

constitution of the audit committee. Corporate governance mechanisms consist of shareholders, board of directors and management. They are viewed in this paper as consisting of ownership structure, board of directors and audit committee. It indicates how firms are governed in order to achieve its objective of maximizing shareholders' wealth. Board ownership indicates the ownership structure of board members or the shareholders they represent. It shows the controlling interests of the company. Board independence indicates the proportion of non-executive directors relative to total board size and it reflects checks over executive directors on behalf of minority shareholders. Diversity is seen here from gender perspective as a proportion of women on the board. According to Nadeem et al. (2019) and Nguyen and Chen (2020), women are more frugal than men and therefore, it is suggested to have more women on the board. Similarly, remuneration is seen to have positive drive towards higher profit. Therefore, the remuneration of board members is considered to be very important in this article. Finally, audit committee size is used as part of corporate governance mechanisms because the committee performs important function of recommending the external auditors to the board and it also reviews auditors' report before final full board consideration. It simply plays a significant role in ensuring earning quality, which shows profitability.

The article objectives are divided into five parts: board ownership, independence, diversity, compensation and audit committee size and their effects on profitability. Based on these sub objectives, the following hypotheses are tested:

H₁: Board ownership has no significant effect on profitability

H₂: Board independence has no significant effect on profitability

H₃: Board gender has no significant effect on profitability

H₄: Board compensation has no significant effect on profitability

H₅: Audit committee size does not significantly influence profitability

A number of stakeholders stand to gain from this article such as researchers, academicians, students, government regulatory agencies, managers, board members, etc. Also, the article offers practical, policy improvements and further research. The scope covers time, space and content boundaries. The remaining parts of the article look at literature review, methodology, results, and discussion of findings, conclusion, and recommendations.

2. Literature Review

There are two primary concepts in this article: corporate governance mechanisms and profitability. CGMs simply revolves around the company's ownership structure, board of directors and its committees and management. It consists of structures put in place in order to ensure that the firm is well run. It is the sets of systems or subsystems of direction that directs board of directors on how to control the organisation. It consists of both internal and external governance structures. However, in this paper, emphasis is on internal corporate governance structures. It is important to note that at the height of CGMs is the concept of supremacy of the shareholders. Without them, there is no company to manage or to control. Core shareholders are expected to constitute the board of directors and which in turn set up board committees: audit, risk, remuneration and nomination committees. Perhaps, the most relevant of these committees to profitability is the audit committee as it works to ensure that earnings management is reduced and therefore, ensure that profitability figure is correct or near perfection. In this paper, corporate governance is seen as consisting of

board shares ownership, independence (composition of non-executive directors), gender, board remuneration and audit committee independence.

Profitability is seen as wealth addition/creation. This might be through gross/net profit margin, or return on: assets, equity, sales, capital employed, investment, etc. It is the degree at which a firm yields profit. Profit is essential, particularly for the continuity of the company. Although, not all corporations are profit-making, it is the pendulum on which future expansions hanged. In practice, it is the difference between receipts and expenses, assuming that all reasonable expenses have been accounted for in an accounting year. In some sectors, it is the difference between success and failure. It is simply the energy to remain in a particular business. It can be seen from several perspectives: ROA, ROE, ROS, ROCE, ROI, etc. In this article, profitability from two angles: ROE and ROA.

Corporate age is used in this article as a control variable. In addition to several other factors, it is a function of profitability or financial performance. It is true that for most firms, age is an advantage. It comes with experiences, lessons and learnings that are not available in the market to purchase. However, it can also be a disadvantage in the sense that it may lead to inertia and complacency on the part of management and workers, thereby retarding profitability or financial performance.

This paper argues that for profitability to be earned, appropriate corporate governance structures must be put in place. The Agency Theory principles recognized the board of directors and by extension, management as representing the interests of shareholders. Thus, in recognition of the divorce between shareholders (principal) and board of directors (agent), a legal relationship is created. This article is hinged on this basic underlying principle.

Several empirical studies have looked at the relationship between corporate governance mechanisms and profitability. Studies have shown that independent directors can help a company make better decisions by keeping an eye on the board (Huson et al., 2001). They found a link between having independent directors and how well a company does. Sanda et al. (2005) argued that the CEO and Chairman positions should be kept separate. Even though the results don't support the idea that boards with a higher percentage of outside directors do better than other firms, there is evidence that firms run by expatriate CEOs tend to do better than those run by CEOs from the same country. Cho and Kim's study from 2007 showed that having outside directors had a small positive effect on profits, but that the rate of ownership by managers had no effect at all.

Ajanthan (2013) found a positive relationship between board size, composition, chief executive officer duality, return on equity, assets, and leverage, but a negative relationship between board size, independence, and debt. The relationship between having two CEOs and using leverage is also positive. Dandago and Gugong (2013) also found that the composition of the board has a positive and significant relationship with both ROE and ROA. The study also found that there was a significant negative relationship between board size and ROA, but there was no relationship between board size and return on equity (ROE). The relationship between being a CEO and ROA ended up being bad, but there is no relationship between being a CEO and ROE.

Basuony et al. (2014) found that there is a strong link between corporate governance and the amount of money a bank makes. Tobin's Q is affected a lot by board size, activism, the number of outside directors, and age. ROA and PM are also affected by how many people own the bank, how often the audit committee meets, how old the bank is, and how big it is. Also, Marashdeh (2014) failed to find any evidence that the size of the board had a big effect on how well a company did. But having duality was good for the company. This means that Jordanian companies do better when there is duality. It was also found that NEDs hurt the performance of a company.

Manini and Abdillahi (2015) found that the size of the audit committee, the number of women on the board, and the amount of money a bank has don't make a big difference in how profitable it is. The regression results show that the size of the board has a negative effect on financial performance, while the size of the bank has a positive effect on financial performance. Also, Igbal and Kakakhel (2015) concluded that board size, independent executives, committees' numbers, compensation, firm size, etc are linked to better corporate achievement.

Yasuhiro et al. (2016) found that Japanese firms with boards dominated by insiders are less profitable and have a lower market value. They said that independent directors could guarantee and encourage people to take risks, which would have a big positive effect on both ROA and Tobin's Q. Nwonyuku (2016) found that the size of a board is related to return on equity and net assets per share in a good way. But board composition shows negative effect on ROE, board skills and competence have negative relationships with ROE, while gender diversity has a positive relationship with ROE.

In 2016, Babatunde and Akeju studied the relationship between corporate governance mechanisms (board characteristics, audit committee, board independence, size, growth, and profit variability) and firms' profitability. At the 0.05 level, the results of the multiple regression analysis were statistically important. The F Statistics of 1.036 also shows that the result usually explained the model. The study's results showed that corporate governance mechanisms help Nigerian firms make more money.

There was a favorable correlation between ROCE and board size, oversight functions, the presence of a risk management system, and the size of the board, as found by Oluwagbemiga (2016). A correlation between executive pay, ownership concentration, and ROCE was not found. The results also showed a favorable correlation between board size, board supervision function, and risk management system, and earnings per share. The correlation between CEO pay and EPS was negative and statistically significant, while the correlation between EPS growth and the role of the board of directors was nil.

In a 2016 study, Surya found that the more best practices in corporate governance a company adopts, the better its financial results. He stated that a negative correlation was established between a higher board size, ownership by promoters, and financial leverage, whereas a positive correlation was identified for board independence, the number of board committees, and director salary. Ultimately, he came to the realization that good company governance and financial success go hand in hand with one another. Research by Arikawa et al. (2017) found that an increase of 29 percent in the number of outside directors leads to an increase of 0.6% in ROA and 0.26% in Tobin's Q. Furthermore, Saito (2009) found that the stock prices of 144 businesses who appointed

their first outside directors responded favorably, increasing by an average of 1.2% and by a median of 1%. Similarly, Sulaiman et al. (2018) discovered that board size, women on boards, board diligence, corporation size have positive significant influences on ROE, whereas board independence, ownership structure, and firm growth have an insignificant effect. Furthermore, Mahrani and Soewarno (2018) demonstrated that the corporate governance mechanism has a positive effect on financial performance. Furthermore, Anandasayanan and Velnampy (2018) discovered that corporate governance has a statistically significant impact on corporate profitability.

According to Abebe and Gebeyehu (2019), the relationship between board gender diversity, board members' political affiliation, and ROA is statistically significant. Furthermore, Gbadebo (2019) discovered that directors' shareholding and block holding had inverse relationships with firm performance. However, board size produced mixed results, with a negative significant influence on return on equity and an inverse but insignificant influence on return on assets. Pham and Nguyen (2019) examined 295 panel datasets of listed firms in Vietnam and discovered significant positive effect of board independence, and ownership. According to Malonza and Mohinder (2019), board size, independence, gender diversity, and competence are all positively and significantly related to profitability.

Junaid et al. (2020) concluded that the most influential internal corporate governance mechanisms on performance are board composition, ownership concentration, and executive compensation. Board composition and executive compensation are significantly correlated with all performance measures, but ownership concentration has a significant positive impact on insurer performance in Pakistan. Furthermore, Nuswantara et al. (2020) discovered that having an independent board of commissioners has a positive effect on bank profitability. The audit committee, the board of directors, and institutional ownership have no effect on bank profitability. Bank profitability is influenced by the size of the company. Furthermore, Inyang et al. (2020) discovered that the composition of the board of directors and the audit committee have no significant relationships with profitability. Moeljadi et al. (2020) demonstrated that corporate governance has no effect on financial performance, whereas independent boards and company size do.

According to Al-Homaidi et al. (2021), board diligence, audit committee size, audit committee composition, audit committee diligence, and company size all have significant relationships with ROA. Board size and composition, on the other hand, have insignificant associations with ROA. The results of the earnings per share (EPS) model revealed that the size of the audit committee, audit committee composition, audit committee diligence, and firm size all have significant relationships with EPS. Board size, board composition, and board diligence, on the other hand, have insignificant associations with EPS. Husnain et al. (2021) unearthed that corporate governance mechanisms, like board size, number of independent directors, and gender diversity, have a strong relation with firm profitability.

The next section is methodology detailing the research design, population, sample and filters, models specification, variables, definitions, measurements and their sources of citation, sources and methods of data collection, techniques of data analysis, diagnostic and post estimation tests, including the criterion for accepting or rejecting their results.

3. Methodology

Correlational research design was used to establish a link between CGMs and PROF, while accounting for corporate age as control variable. 130 balanced panel dataset for a period of 10 years covering 2010-2019 was tested using correlation matrix and multiple regression analysis techniques. However, the dataset was checked for presence or absence of normality, heteroskedasticity, multicollinearity, panel effect and Hausman specification. The data used were based on (1) only banks were considered (2) banks with complete 10-years annual reports were included (3) banks that were listed after 2010 were not considered. The baseline models of the article were adapted from Pham and Nguyen (2019) and amended to reflect effect of corporate age on profitability:

$$\text{PROF}_{i,t} = \beta_0 + \beta_1\text{BO}_{i,t} + \beta_2\text{BI}_{i,t} + \beta_3\text{BG}_{i,t} + \beta_4\text{BC}_{i,t} + \beta_5\text{ACS}_{i,t} + \beta_6\text{AGE}_{i,t} + \varepsilon_{i,t} \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Thus, empirically tested models include:

$$\text{ROE}_{i,t} = \beta_0 + \beta_1\text{BO}_{i,t} + \beta_2\text{BI}_{i,t} + \beta_3\text{BG}_{i,t} + \beta_4\text{BC}_{i,t} + \beta_5\text{ACS}_{i,t} + \beta_6\text{AGE}_{i,t} + \varepsilon_{i,t} \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

$$\text{ROA}_{i,t} = \beta_0 + \beta_1\text{BO}_{i,t} + \beta_2\text{BI}_{i,t} + \beta_3\text{BG}_{i,t} + \beta_4\text{BC}_{i,t} + \beta_5\text{ACS}_{i,t} + \beta_6\text{AGE}_{i,t} + \varepsilon_{i,t} \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

Where:

PROF = Profitability or financial performance, represented by ROA (profit after tax divided by total assets, %) and ROE (profit after tax divided by total equity, %) as reported by Yahaya and Lamidi (2015) and Yahaya (2018).

α = Constant

β_{1-6} = Beta (coefficients)

ε = Error term

BO = Board ownership (representing ownership structure) measured as directors' direct and indirect shares divided by the numbers of shares (%) as indicated by Westman (2020).

BI = Board independence, represented by the non-executive board of directors divided by total board size (%) as used in Husnain et al. (2021) and El-Chaarani et al. (2022)

BG = Board gender, proportion of women directors as a fraction of total number of directors (%) as used by Islam et al. (2018)

BC = Board compensation, measured as total director remuneration divided by sales or revenue (%) as used by Akter et al. (2020)

ACS = Audit committee size is the total directors and non-directors in the audit committee (%) as used by Salehi et al. (2018)

AGE = Corporate age is computed based on base year (2022) minus year of listing (Akben-Selcuk, 2016)

i = Firm script (i = 13 firms)

t = Time script (t = 10 years)

4. Results and discussion

The first result to be displayed in this article is the result of descriptive statistics. It provides a pictorial view of the data used. Several types are available, however, the types used in this article are mean (average), standard deviations (dispersion or volatility), minimum (lowest), maximum (highest) and the number of observations (number of firms multiplied by number of years). The variables are categorised into overall, between and within variances. The result is reported in Table 1 as follows:

Table 1
Descriptive Statistics

Variables	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max	Observations
ROE:	10.89	9.43	-12.20	32.08	N = 130
between		7.62	-1.67	26.26	n = 13
within		5.90	-8.72	32.80	T = 10
ROA:	1.48	2.36	-9.53	9.54	Applicable to all variables
between		1.35	-.79	4.40	
within		1.96	-7.88	9.84	
BO:	9.91	14.62	.00	71.60	
between		12.90	.18	37.84	
within		7.68	-24.83	45.22	
BI:	60.58	11.76	36.84	90	
between		9.22	48.65	74.75	
within		7.68	41.13	79.37	
BG:	16.81	10.67	0	60	
between		7.56	2.58	31.49	
within		7.78	-2.76	45.32	
BC:	.44	.27	.01	.98	
between		.14	.19	.67	
within		.24	-.09	.99	
ACS:	6.05	.45	4	9	
between		.17	5.8	6.4	
within		.42	4.25	8.65	
AGE:	25.89	15.53	5	53	
between		15.20	9.5	48.5	
within		2.88	21.39	30.38	

Source: STATA 14 Outputs

As shown in Table 1, the total number of observations for all of the variables is 130, which comes from multiplying the 10 years of data by the 13 banks. It shows that the panel data were balanced for the years and variables that were looked at, which is in line with the filters that were used. In the same way, the average rate of return on equity (ROE) was 10.89%, with an exposure to risk of 9.43% and a least mean of -12.20% and a maximum mean of 32.08%. Maybe it's important to know that the total variance is 88.85 (9.432), of which the between variance is 58.13 (7.432) and the within variance is 34.77. (5.9072). In the same way, the average ROA is 1.48 percent, and the maximum and least rates are -9.53 percent and 9.54 percent, respectively. Even though this number is low compared to the ROE, this is because of how the measurement was done. Some authors calculated ROA by dividing profit after taxes by total assets, while others used profit before taxes and interest. Also, the total variance is 5.55 (2.362), which is made up of a between variance of 1.83 (1.352) and a within variance of 3.14. (1.962). Also, the average board independence rate is 6.57 percent, with an exposure to risk of 11.76 percent and least and maximum rates of 36.84 percent and 90 percent, respectively. The total variance is 85 (9.222), of which 58.98 (7.682) is between variance and 3.14 is within variance (1.962).

Also, the average board ownership (BO) is 9.91 percent, the exposure to risk is 14.92 percent, and the lowest rate is .00 percent and the highest rate is 72 percent. Also, the total variance, which is 222.61 (14.922), can be broken down into two parts: between variance, which is 166.41 (12.902), and within variance, which is 58.98. (7.682). The average level of board independence (BI) is 60.58 percent, with an exposure to risk of 11.76 percent, a least rate of 36.84 percent, and a maximum rate of 90 percent. Also, the total variance, which is 138.30 (11.762), can be broken down into two parts: between variance, which is 85.01 (9.222), and within variance, which is 58.98. (7.682). Also, the mean of board gender (BG) is 16.81%, the exposure to risk is 10.67%, and the lowest and highest rates are 0% and 60%, respectively. Also, the total variance, which is 113.85 (10.672), can be broken down into two parts: between variance, which is 57.15 (7.562), and within variance, which is 60.53. (7.782). Also, the average board compensation (BC) rate is .44%, with a risk exposure of .27%, least and maximum rates of .1% and 98%, respectively. Also, the total variance, which is .0729 (.272), is broken down into two parts: between variance, which is .0196 (.142), and within variance, which is .0576 (.242).

The average size of an audit committee (ACS) is 6.05, with a risk exposure of 0.45 and a least size of 4 and a maximum size of 9. Also, the total variance, which is .0729 (.452), is broken down into two parts: between variance, which is .0196 (.172), and within variance, which is .0576 (.422). Lastly, the average age of the banks was 26 years old, with a risk exposure of 16 years and a range of ages from 5 to 53. But the total variance, 256 (162), can be broken down into two parts: between variance, which is 225 (152), and within variance, which is 9. (32). Table 2 shows how the Pearson Correlation method shows how strong the link is between corporate governance mechanisms and profitability. But it's important to remember that correlation works in both directions, and only two variables are used at a time. Davies (1971) says that correlation coefficients between .01 and .09 are not very important, .1 and .29 are low, .30 and .49 are average, .5 and .69 are important, .7 and .99 are very important, and 1 is perfect.

Table 2
Pairwise correlations

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)
(1) ROE	1.000							
(2) ROA	0.658*	1.000						
	(0.000)							
(3) BO	-0.196*	-0.340*	1.000					
	(0.025)	(0.000)						
(4) BI	-0.141*	-0.164*	-0.105*	1.000				
	(0.108)	(0.062)	(0.237)					
(5) BG	0.311*	0.126*	-0.163*	-0.036	1.000			
	(0.000)	(0.153)	(0.063)	(0.684)				
(6) BC	-0.296*	-0.040	-0.116*	0.188*	-0.133*	1.000		
	(0.001)	(0.651)	(0.187)	(0.032)	(0.132)			
(7) ACS	0.145*	0.164*	-0.046	-0.101*	0.078*	0.010	1.000	
	(0.101)	(0.062)	(0.607)	(0.253)	(0.381)	(0.912)		
(8) AGE	-0.112*	-0.005	-0.181*	-0.159*	0.033	-0.132*	0.042	1.000
	(0.203)	(0.955)	(0.039)	(0.071)	(0.707)	(0.133)	(0.639)	

*** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$

Source: STATA 14 Outputs

Based on the results in Table 2, two classes of findings can be observed: weak and moderate. There is simply no finding to support strong association. The association between return on equity and gender is slightly moderate, positive and significant ($r = .311^*$). Return on equity and board ownership, independence, compensation are weak, negative and significant, but return on equity and audit committee size is weak, positive and significant. On the other hand, return on assets and ownership, independence are weak, negative and significant, however, return on assets and board gender, compensation and audit committee size are weak, positive and significant. The next level of analysis in this article is regression. For this purpose, three competing techniques are available: pooled, random and fixed effect models.

Pooled Model

Table 3

Model 1 OLS

ROE	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Cnf	Interval]	Sig
BO	-.157	.052	-3.01	.003	-.261	-.054	***
BI	-.102	.064	-1.58	.117	-.229	.026	
BG	.199	.07	2.84	.005	.06	.338	***
BC	-10.381	2.77	-3.75	.0	-15.864	-4.898	***
ACS	2.401	1.616	1.49	.14	-.798	5.601	
AGE	-.139	.049	-2.85	.005	-.236	-.042	***
Constant	8.88	11.13	0.80	.427	-13.152	30.911	
Mean dependent var		10.892	SD dependent var			9.426	
R-squared		0.268	Number of obs			130	
F-test		7.499	Prob > F			0.000	
Akaike crit. (AIC)		924.688	Bayesian crit. (BIC)			944.761	

***@.01, **.05, *.1

Source: STATA 14 Outputs

Table 3 made it clear that there were two main results: ROE has a big negative effect on board ownership and pay, but a small negative effect on the board's independence. Return on equity shows that gender has a positive, significant effect and that the size of the audit committee has a positive, but not very significant effect. In terms of the control variable, age has a negative and significant effect on return on equity.

Table 4

Model 2 OLS

ROA	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Cnf	Interval]	Sig
BO	-.06	.014	-4.39	0.00	-.088	-.033	***
BI	-.039	.017	-2.33	.022	-.073	-.006	**
BG	.01	.018	0.52	.601	-.027	.046	
BC	-.498	.728	-0.68	.496	-1.939	.943	
ACS	.671	.425	1.58	.117	-.17	1.512	
AGE	-.018	.013	-1.40	.163	-.043	.007	
Constant	.924	2.925	0.32	.753	-4.866	6.714	
Mean dependent var		1.482	SD dependent var			2.355	
R-squared		0.190	Number of obs			130	
F-test		4.797	Prob > F			0.000	
Akaike crit. (AIC)		577.242	Bayesian crit. (BIC)			597.315	

***@.01, **.05, *.1

Source: STATA 14 Outputs

Table 4 shows that the return on assets has a negative, but not very important, effect on ownership and independence, but has no effect at all on compensation. On the plus side, it shows that there is a positive but not very important effect on gender and the size of the audit committee. Return on assets has a negative, but not very important, effect on the control variable. When the pooled technique is used, the panel nature of the data is not taken into account, and the error term is treated as if it were equal and spread out on its own. The next question is how to account for the individual effects in the data set on which these results are computed. In this regard, two competing options are the random effects (REM) and fixed effects models (FEM). The results in Tables 5 and 6 are based on REM and FEM, respectively.

Table 5

Model 1 Random Effects Model

R O E	Coeff.	Std.Er.	t-val	p-val	[.95 Cnf	Interv]	Sig
BO	-.168	.063	-2.68	.007	-.291	-.045	***
BI	.021	.067	0.31	.756	-.111	.153	
BG	.034	.067	0.51	.607	-.097	.166	
BC	-5.437	2.254	-2.41	.016	-9.855	-1.019	**
ACS	-.577	1.274	-0.45	.65	-3.074	1.919	
AGE	-.184	.096	-1.92	.054	-.372	.004	*
Constant	21.363	9.461	2.26	.024	2.82	39.906	**
Mean dependent var		10.892	SD dependent var			9.426	
Overall r-squared		0.130	Number of obs			130	
Chi-square		16.794	Prob > chi2			0.010	
R-squared within		0.117	R-squared between			0.138	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Source: STATA 14 Outputs

The results in Table 5 show that ROE has negative significant effect on ownership and audit committee size and positive insignificant effect on independence and gender. However, it shows negative insignificant effect on age.

Table 6

Model 2 Random Effects Model

R O A	Coeff.	Std.Er.	t-val	p-val	[.95 Cnf	Interv]	Sig
BO	-.062	.015	-4.19	0.00	-.092	-.033	***
BI	-.039	.018	-2.17	.03	-.074	-.004	**
BG	.002	.019	0.12	.905	-.035	.04	
BC	-.232	.725	-0.32	.749	-1.654	1.189	
ACS	.517	.419	1.23	.217	-.304	1.339	
AGE	-.017	.015	-1.16	.246	-.046	.012	
Constant	1.819	2.904	0.63	.531	-3.873	7.51	
Mean dependent var		1.482	SD dependent var			2.355	
Overall r-squared		0.186	Number of obs			130	
Chi-square		23.610	Prob > chi2			0.001	
R-squared within		0.074	R-squared between			0.447	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Source: STATA 14 Outputs

Table 6 shows that ROA has a negative significant effect on ownership size and independence size, a negative but not very important effect on compensation, and a positive but not very important effect on audit committee size and gender. However, it has a small but negative effect on age. The next big question is whether to use OLS or REM with the results. The Breusch-Pagan, Lagrangian Multiplier (LM) Test becomes important at this point.

Table 7

Breusch and Pagan, Lagrangian Multiplier Test

Models	chibar ² (01)	Probab > chibar ²
ROE	65.92	.0000
ROA	5.03	.0124

Source: STATA 14 Outputs

Table 7 shows that both models are significant, which means that the data set has panel effects and that neither model can use OLS. The next thing to figure out is which of the two panel effects models, REM or FEM, is better. Here, the Hausman Specification test comes into play.

Table 8

Hausman Specification Test Results

Models	chibar ² (06)	Probab > chi ²
ROE	7.12	.3101
ROA	Model fitted on these data fails to meet the asymptotic assumptions of the Hausman test	

Source: STATA 14 Outputs

Based on the results in Table 8, the ROA Model is completely thrown out because the data does not meet the assumptions for the Hausman Specification Test. In other words, the models are not different from each other. Since the two models come from the same family, this makes sense. Also, the results show that the ROE Model isn't important, which means that the Random Effects Model (REM), also called Generalized Least Squares (GLS), is the most useful. Before the article decides on the final regression methods, it needs to do post-estimation tests on normality, multicollinearity, heteroskedasticity, linearity, serial correlation (dependence), etc. The results of the test of multicollinearity are shown in Table 9.

Table 9

ROE Multicollinearity Results

Variables	VIF	1/VIF
AGE	1.13	.885
BC	1.10	.906
BO	1.09	.921
BI	1.06	.944
BG	1.05	.955
ACS	1.04	.965
Mean VIF	1.08	

Source: STATA 14 Outputs

From the VIF results in Table 9, it show that there is no presence of multicollinearity in the model and therefore, all the variables can remain. Table 10 reports the results of heteroskedasticity test.

Table 10

ROE Cameron and Trivedi's decomposition of IM-test (heteroskedasticity) results

Source	chi ²	df	p
Heteroskedasticity	10.68	27	.998
Skewness	3.84	6	.698
Kurtosis	1.08	1	.299
Total	15.59	34	.997

Source: STATA 14 Outputs

The results of the information matrix (IM) test and orthogonal decomposition for heteroskedasticity, skewness, and kurtosis are shown in Table 10. Based on the results, the p-value for ROE is not significant, which means it is higher than 5%. This means that the model does not have heteroskedasticity. In Table 11, the results of the serial correlation test are shown. The Wooldridge Test was used to find a link between two or more events.

Table 11

Wooldridge test for autocorrelation in panel data (Independence)

Model	F(1, 12)	Prob > F
ROE	8.12	.0146

Source: STATA 14 Outputs

Premised on Table 11, the paper says that the data has first order serial autocorrelation because the p-value is significant, which means that there is serial correlation. To fix the serial correlation, this means you need to use either autocorrelated AR (1) or panel corrected standard errors (xtpcse).

Table 12

Serial Correlation Corrected REM Regression Results

ROE	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
BO	-.198	.065	-3.05	.002	-.325	-.071	***
BI	0	.071	0.01	.994	-.139	.14	
BG	.043	.068	0.64	.52	-.089	.176	
BC	-.0564	2.246	-2.51	.012	-10.042	-1.238	**
ACS	-.17	1.212	-0.14	.889	-2.546	2.206	
AGE	-.158	.093	-1.71	.088	-.34	.023	*
Constant	19.724	9.162	2.15	.031	1.766	37.682	**
Mean dependent var		10.892	SD dependent var			9.426	
Overall r-squared		0.159	Number of obs			130	
Chi-square		17.647	Prob > chi ²			0.014	
R-squared within		0.104	R-squared between			0.198	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Source: STATA 14 Outputs

Table 12 shows that return on equity has a negative, significant effect on who owns the board, how much people are paid, and how old the firm is. The implication is that a unit increase in board

share ownership means a 19.8 percent decrease in return on equity, and a unit increase in compensation means a 5.6 percent decrease in profitability. The study didn't find any link between gender and being on your own. The results also show that older firms don't do as well as newer ones. This could be caused by laziness and a lack of motivation. But it has a small but positive effect on gender and independence. It has a small but negative effect on the size of audit committees. It also shows that the model fits (Prob > chi2 =.014) and that r2 is 15.9% overall. The effect size study says that this percentage is quite big. It means that corporate governance and the age of the company explain about 16% of the change in ROE. The last step of the analysis is to check if the residual (e) is normal. The results are shown in Table 13:

Table 13

Shapiro-Wilk W test for normal data

Variable	Obs	W	V	z	Prob>z
e	130	0.992	0.839	-0.394	0.653

Source: STATA 14 Outputs

The value of Probability greater than z in Table 13 is insignificant, that is, it is greater than 5%, which suggests that the residual is normally and independently distributed. Hence the data shows absence of normality problem.

Conclusions and Recommendations

To summarize, two corporate governance variables are important: board ownership and audit committee size. As a result, managers of the banks under consideration should take practical steps to reduce (i) the number of shares held by directors and (ii) the size of the audit committee to the bare minimum, in this case, six. In particular, Abbey Mortgage Bank recorded a negative ROE during the period under consideration; this scenario is not healthy for the bank, and management should wake up and take measures to increase profit. FCMB, Unity Bank, Union Bank, and Wema Bank have all made strides in this regard. In addition, Wema Bank's management should increase board members' shares to increase their motivation. To motivate board members, Sterling Bank should increase their pay. Women should be appointed to the boards of directors of First City Monument Bank, Sterling Bank, and Unity Bank. It is commendable that both First Bank and Zenith Bank have taken corrective action in this matter. Abbey Mortgage Bank and FCMB have expanded their audit committee from four to six members. Furthermore, despite the fact that the article found board independence and gender to be positively insignificant, it is recommended that bank executives significantly increase the number of non-executive directors and women on the board of directors. Finally, it is suggested that bank executives avoid relying on past accomplishments, which leads to complacency, inertia, and procrastination.

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